

Comparative studies of haemoglobin variants in normal, sickle cell trait, sickle cell disease and β -thalassemia trait patients using cellulose acetate electrophoresis and cation exchange-high performance liquid chromatography

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Abstract : Approximately 5% of the world's population carries trait genes for haemoglobin disorders, mainly, sickle cell disease and thalassemia. Haemoglobin disorders are genetic blood diseases due to inheritance of mutant haemoglobin genes from both, generally healthy parents. Sickle cell disease and β -thalassaemia are most common in eastern province of Saudi Arabia. The present study was undertaken to analyze the variation in levels of haemoglobin (Hb) types in different haemoglobin disorders in samples of patients from Riyadh, Saudi Arabia by CAE and HPLC method and to identify the best and effective method for diagnosis of different types of Hb disorders. In the present prospective study blood samples from four groups – normal healthy males and females, sickle cell trait, sickle cell disease and β -thalassemia patients were included. The levels of Hb variants such as HbA, HbA₂, HbF and HbS were measured by two techniques – cellulose acetate electrophoresis (CAE) and cation exchange-high performance liquid chromatography (CE-HPLC). There was a significant increase ($p < 0.001$) in levels of HbA₂ in patients with β -thalassemia compared to normal and sickle cell trait/disease. The levels of HbF and HbS increased significantly ($p < 0.001$) in patients with sickle cell disease compared to other groups. The HPLC chromatogram of Hb variants acts as fingerprint for diagnosis of different haemoglobinopathies. The separation and analysis of different Hb fractions was achieved effectively using HPLC when compared to cellulose acetate electrophoresis. The present study facilitates clear understanding of changes in levels of Hb fractions in different types of haemoglobinopathies and also proves HPLC as the best technique that can be used for diagnosis of the disease. HPLC was found to be more efficient method due to high sensitivity and resolution compared to cellulose acetate electrophoresis.

Keywords : Haemoglobin, sickle cell disease, sickle cell trait, β -thalassemia, HPLC, CAE.

Introduction

Haemoglobin variants are a part of the normal embryonic and fetal development, but may also be pathologic mutant forms of haemoglobin in a population, caused by variations in genetics. Some well-known haemoglobin variants such as sickle cell anemia are responsible for diseases, and are considered haemoglobinopathies. Other variants cause no detectable pathology, and are thus considered non-pathological variants¹. Normal haemoglobin types include : Haemoglobin A (HbA) comprise about 95–98% of Hb found in adults and contains two alpha (α) protein chains and two beta (β) protein chains. Haemoglobin A₂ (HbA₂) is minor haemoglobin in adult red cell

and makes up about 2–3% of Hb. It has two alpha (α) and two delta (δ) protein chains. Elevation of HbA₂ is a feature of some types of thalassemia and megaloblastic anemia. HbA₂ may be reduced in iron deficiency. Haemoglobin F (HbF) makes up to 2% of Hb found in adults and has two alpha (α) and two gamma (γ) protein chains and is the primary haemoglobin produced by the fetus during pregnancy. Its production usually falls to a low level shortly after birth. HbF is elevated in some haemoglobinopathies and thalassemia syndromes. Elevated HbF has been demonstrated in sickle cell anaemia and β -thalassemia².

Abnormal haemoglobin :

Structural haemoglobin (Hb) variants typically are based on a point mutation in a globin gene that produces a single aminoacid substitution in globin chain³. Wajcman (2001), reviewed laboratory techniques used for detection and characterization of haemoglobin variants⁴. Haemoglobin abnormalities results in qualitative, quantitative abnormalities and mixed type of syndrome. Qualitative abnormalities results due to synthesis of abnormal haemoglobin which arises from synthesis of α or β chain with an aminoacid substitution. This group includes HbS, HbC, HbD and HbE. Quantitative abnormalities are due to reduced rate of synthesis of normal α or β globin chain, which leads to α -thalassemia or β -thalassemia syndrome. Third type include mixed syndrome : combined abnormal haemoglobin and reduced chain production for example S/thalassemia syndrome.

Common haemoglobin variants :

Haemoglobin S : This is the primary haemoglobin in people with sickle cell disease. Approximately 8% of Americans of African descent carry the sickle Hb mutation in one of their two beta genes (0.15% of African Americans have sickle cell disease). Those with HbS disease have two abnormal beta (β^S) chains and two normal alpha (α) chains. The presence of haemoglobin S causes the red blood cell to deform and assume a sickle shape when exposed to decreased amounts of oxygen (such as might happen when someone exercises). Sickled red blood cells can block small blood vessels, causing pain and impaired circulation, decrease the oxygen-carrying capacity of the red blood cell, and decrease the cell's life span. Sickling of erythrocytes is accompanied by increase in temperature, decreased pH (acidosis) and high MCHC (dehydration).

Haemoglobin C : About 2–3% of people of West African descent are heterozygotes for haemoglobin C (have one copy of β^C). Haemoglobin C disease (seen in homozygotes – those with two copies of β^C) is rare and relatively mild. It usually causes a minor amount of hemolytic anaemia and a mild to moderate enlargement of the spleen.

Haemoglobin E : Haemoglobin E is one of the most

common beta chain haemoglobin variants in the world. It is very prevalent in Southeast Asia, especially in Cambodia, Laos, and Thailand and in individuals of Southeast Asian descent. People who are homozygous for HbE (have two copies of β^E) generally have a mild haemolytic anaemia, microcytic red blood cells, and a mild enlargement of the spleen. A single copy of the haemoglobin E gene does not cause symptoms unless it is combined with another mutation, such as the one for β -thalassemia trait.

The inherited haemoglobinopathies are large group of disorders that include the thalassemias and sickle cell disease. Measurement of haemoglobin Hb A₂, S and F has a great clinical value in the diagnosis as well as in characterization of some Hb structural variants and other hemoglobinopathies. In particular, increase in the HbA₂ level is considered to be the most characteristic diagnostic feature of β -thalassemia trait and the determination of this Hb component represents an essential test in the screening programs for β -thalassemia prevention⁵.

Sickle cell anemia :

Prevalence in Saudi Arabia : Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a common hereditary blood disease in Saudi Arabia. The gene for sickle cell haemoglobin (HbS) results in substitution of valine for glutamic acid normally present at the sixth position in beta chain of haemoglobin molecule⁶. SCD in Saudi Arabia was first reported in the Eastern province in the 1960s⁷. The reported prevalence for sickle cell trait ranges from 2% to 27%, and up to 2.6% will have SCD in some areas⁸. Sickle cell trait is characterized by the inheritance of a normal haemoglobin gene (HbA) from one parent and an abnormal, mutated β_1 -globin gene, the sickle haemoglobin gene (HbS), from the other parent⁹.

Thalassemia :

Thalassemia results due to quantitative abnormality of haemoglobin. Thalassemia is caused by impaired production of either the alpha or beta haemoglobin chain and is accordingly classified as alpha or beta thalassemia. Alpha thalassemia is relatively rare, whereas beta thalassemia is quite common in certain parts of the world. Al-Awamy BH (2004), found that β -thalassemia major that occurs mostly in Mediterranean region is also prevalent with a

variable frequency in different regions of Saudi Arabia and the incidence in the eastern province is 10%¹⁰. Clinical manifestations include microcytic hypochromic erythrocytes, MCV and MCH very low but high red cell count and mild anemia with splenomegaly.

The laboratory diagnosis of haemoglobinopathies – sickle cell anemia and thalassemias can be achieved by a step-wise approach starting with a detailed clinical history, thorough haematologic evaluation including haemoglobin level, complete blood count (CBC), reticulocyte count, and red blood cell (RBC) morphology and protein based analytic methods like alkaline and acid Hb-electrophoresis, isoelectric focusing (IEF) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)¹¹. There are many electrophoretic and chromatographic approaches for estimation of HbA₂ and HbF but CE-HPLC (cation exchange-high performance liquid chromatography) using automated dedicated machines like the variant Hb testing system have become the method of choice for these investigations¹². CE-HPLC also helps in the presumptive identification of many abnormal haemoglobin variants and has been useful for both neonatal screening of sickle cell disease as well as second trimester prenatal diagnosis of thalassemia by fetal blood analysis.

The present study was undertaken to analyze the levels of different haemoglobin variants – HbA, HbA₂, HbF and HbS in normal healthy persons, sickle cell anaemic patients, persons with sickle cell traits and β -thalassemia trait using Cellulose Acetate Electrophoresis (CAE) and HPLC method. The levels of haemoglobin variants were analyzed in different types of haemoglobin disorders and the results obtained by CAE were compared with cation exchange-high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) to determine the best method for screening different types of haemoglobinopathies.

Materials and methods :

Study design :

This was a cross-sectional randomized study designed to investigate the levels of abnormal haemoglobin in normal and patients with certain type of haemoglobinopathy.

Subject population :

The present study was carried out in King Khalid University Hospital, Riyadh. A total of 200 samples with suspected haemoglobinopathies were investigated. The

study population included normal healthy persons (23 males and 27 females), patients with sickle cell disease (50), patients with sickle cell trait (50) and patients with β -thalassemia trait (50). In all abnormal cases, family studies were carried out. Informed consent was obtained from each of the subjects after the study was explained to them. The study received the approval of the ethical committee of King Khalid University Hospital, Riyadh.

Blood sample collection :

Two to five millimeters of venous blood was collected in tubes containing EDTA, from healthy persons, patients with sickle cell disease (HbSS), patients with sickle cell trait (HbAS) and patients with β -thalassemia trait. All samples were stored at 2–8 °C and tested within one week of collection

Biochemical analysis :

Blood samples were processed for analysis of complete blood count (CBC) which was performed from the anti-coagulated blood including estimation of haemoglobin (Hb), haematocrit (Hct), RBC and RBC indices. Haemoglobin was measured by Cyanmethaemoglobin Spectroscopic method. Other parameters were measured directly, from Coulter Counter (STK-S).

Haemoglobin A, A₂, F and S were separated and analyzed by cellulose acetate electrophoresis (CAE) and CE-HPLC. Haemoglobin analysis and quantitation were performed by HPLC VARIANT (Biorad Laboratories, UK). Cellulose acetate electrophoresis at pH 8.2–8.6 was performed on Helena Titan III cellulose acetate plates and haemoglobin A, A₂, F and S were then measured by scanning densitometry. Finally results obtained in CAE were compared with HPLC.

Statistical analysis :

Values were expressed as mean \pm SD. The level of significance between different groups is based on Dunnett's *t*-test followed by analysis of variance. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to calculate the statistical significance between various groups. A value of *p* < 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results

Complete blood count (CBC) : Results of CBC, including the mean values of Hb, Hct, RBC, MCV, MCHC, and % retics in normal and disease samples are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Complete blood count (CBC) values in normal and diseased samples

Groups	Value	Hb (g/L)	RBC ($\times 10^{12}/L$)	Hct (CL/L)	MCV (fl)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (g/dl)	Retices (%)
Normal male	Mean	13.28	4.81	39.73	82.55	27.57	33.41	1.14
	SD	0.94	0.29	2.76	3.15	0.80	0.62	0.57
Normal female	Mean	12.57	4.62	37.95	82.19	27.32	33.17	1.49
	SD	1.21	0.3	3.32	2.44	1.39	0.60	0.72
Sickle cell trait	Mean	11.70 ^a	4.60	34.73 ^a	74.73 ^b	25.35	33.86	0.67
	SD	1.31	0.70	3.55	3.66	1.80	1.30	0.27
Sickle cell disease	Mean	9.04 ^b	3.30 ^b	27.08 ^b	88.60 ^b	27.59	33.39	6.28 ^b
	SD	1.58	0.76	4.38	3.97	4.23	1.15	1.23
β -Thalassemia	Mean	11.78	6.03 ^b	35.93	59.61 ^b	19.53 ^b	32.83	0.91
	SD	1.21	0.59	4.19	3.56	1.15	0.61	0.40

^aSignificantly different ($p < 0.05$) when compared with normal samples.

^bSignificantly different ($p < 0.001$) when compared with normal samples.

Estimation of Hb variants by CAE and CE-HPLC method : Cellulose acetate electrophoretic pattern or chromatogram of patient with normal, sickle cell trait, sickle cell disease and β -thalassemia are shown in Fig. 1 and graphical output of the VARIANT haemoglobin testing system with retention time are shown in Fig. 2.

HbA, HbA₂, HbF and HbS in normal samples : Results of different types of Hb are shown in Table 2.

Haemoglobin A : HbA estimated by CAE was found

Fig. 1. Cellulose acetate electrophoresis pattern at alkaline pH (8.6) : (A) normal subject, (B) sickle cell trait samples, (C) sickle cell patient samples showing HbF and (D) β -thalassemia trait.

Fig. 2. Graphical output of the variant haemoglobin testing system (HPLC) : T = retention time in minutes, (A) normal subject; HbA = 97.4%, HbF = 0%, HbA₂ = 2.2%; (B) sickle cell trait; HbA = 67%, HbS = 27.8%, HbA₂ = 3.7%, HbF < 1.0%; (C) sickle cell patient; HbA = 0%, HbS = 89.2%, HbF = 6.7%, HbA₂ = 4.5% and (D) β -thalassemia trait; HbF = 0.3%, HbA₂ = 4.9%.

in range from 97–98% in normal males with a mean value of 97.5%, and in females the value was observed in range from 97–98.4% (mean value of 97.46%). By HPLC method, the levels of HbA range from 96.5–97.70% in males and 95.0–97.8% in females (mean values; males – 97.14%, females – 97.27%).

Haemoglobin A₂ : Values of HbA₂ by CAE in normal

Table 2. Mean values of Hb variant by CAE and HPLC

Method	Hb variant	Normal male	Normal female	Sickle cell trait	Sickle cell disease	β -Thalassemia
Cellulose acetate electrophoresis (CAE)	HbA	97.5 \pm 0.36	97.46 \pm 0.44	58.38 \pm 11.65 ^b	0.00	91.38 \pm 4.39 ^a
	HbA ₂	2.39 \pm 0.34	2.55 \pm 0.44	3.71 \pm 0.95 ^b	3.72 \pm 1.55	5.42 \pm 1.08 ^b
	HbF	0.10 \pm 0.32	0.0	0.79 \pm 2.5 ^b	18.15 \pm 9.41 ^b	3.20 \pm 4.61 ^b
	HbS	0.0	0.0	37.10 \pm 9.3 ^b	78.13 \pm 8.25 ^b	0.0
HPLC	HbA	97.14 \pm 0.41	97.27 \pm 0.68	58.96 \pm 12.69 ^b	0.0	90.56 \pm 5.00 ^a
	HbA ₂	2.46 \pm 0.24	2.47 \pm 0.25	4.15 \pm 0.58 ^b	3.96 \pm 1.43	5.44 \pm 1.21 ^b
	HbF	0.40 \pm 0.46	0.26 \pm 0.50	1.53 \pm 2.06 ^b	16.54 \pm 8.71 ^b	4.00 \pm 4.92 ^b
	HbS	0.0	0.0	35.24 \pm 10.78	79.5 \pm 7.63 ^b	0.0

Each value represents mean \pm S.E. of ten samples.

^aSignificantly different ($p < 0.05$) when compared with normal samples.

^bSignificantly different ($p < 0.001$) when compared with normal samples.

male ranges from 2.00–2.76% with a mean value 2.39% and in females the value was observed in range from 1.60–3.00% (mean value – 2.55). By HPLC analysis, the HbA₂ value was in the range of 2.10–2.60% in males and in females the value ranges from 2.20–2.90% with mean value of 2.46% in males and 2.47% in females.

Haemoglobin F : HbF estimated by CAE ranges from 0–1% in normal males and 0–1.4% in females, whereas by HPLC, it was 0–1.4% with a mean of 0.40% in males and 0–1.6% (mean value 0.26%) in females.

Sickle cell trait :

Haemoglobin A : HbA estimated by CAE in samples with sickle cell trait was found in range of 29.50–72.4%, with a mean value of 58.38% and by HPLC, HbA value ranges from 28.80–78.70% with a mean value of 58.96%. The HbA levels were found to be significantly lower ($p < 0.001$) in patients with sickle cell trait compared to normal samples.

Haemoglobin A₂ : HbA₂ levels estimated by CAE in samples with sickle cell trait were found in range of 2.4–4.9%, with a mean value of 3.71% and by HPLC, HbA₂ value ranges 3.10–4.80% and a mean value of 4.15%. The HbA₂ levels was found to increase significantly ($p < 0.001$) in patients with sickle cell trait compared to normal samples.

Haemoglobin F : There was significant increase in HbF values in both the methods, CAE and HPLC in samples with sickle cell trait when compared with normal samples ($p < 0.001$).

Haemoglobin S : In samples analysed for HbS by CAE, the values were observed in range from 24.50–58.60% with mean value of 37.10% and by HPLC method the values range from 17.40–59.2%, with a mean value of 35.24%. The levels of HbS were found to increase significantly ($p < 0.001$) in patients with sickle cell trait compared to normal.

Sickle cell anaemia : Values of different types of Hb are shown in Table 2.

Haemoglobin A : In samples suspected of sickle cell anaemia, there was no value observed for HbA by both CAE and HPLC.

Haemoglobin A₂ : HbA₂ estimated by CAE was found in range from 1.10–6.20% with a mean value of 3.72% and by HPLC, the range was 2.00–6.30% with a mean value of 3.96%.

Haemoglobin F : HbF in sickle cell disease samples was estimated by CAE was observed to be in range of 10.10–33.70% with a mean value of 18.15% and by HPLC, range was observed to be from 7.5–32.3% (mean value of 16.54%). The levels of HbF was significantly higher than normal samples ($p < 0.001$).

Haemoglobin S : HbS value estimated in sickle cell disease patients was observed in a range from 65.20–86.60% with a mean value of 78.13% by CAE and by HPLC, the value range from 65.70–88.90% with a mean value of 79.50%. The values of HbS were found to be significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) in samples with sickle cell anemia compared to normal samples and sickle cell trait samples.

β-Thalassemia :

Haemoglobin A : The value of HbA estimated by CAE, was observed in range from 82.30–95.20% with a mean value of 91.38%. The value obtained was found to be significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared to normal samples. HbA values obtained by HPLC was in range from 80.30–95.10% with a mean value 90.56% which was observed to be significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared to normal subjects.

Haemoglobin A₂ : HbA₂ estimated by CAE was observed in a range from 4.3–7.9% with a mean value of 5.42% and by HPLC method, the value range from 4.10–8.4% (mean value 5.44%). The levels of HbA₂ estimated by CAE and HPLC was observed to be significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) in samples of patients with β -thalassemia trait when compared to normal samples and other types of Hb disorders.

Haemoglobin F : HbF estimated by CAE ranges from 0–12.80% with a mean value of 3.20% and by HPLC the value ranges from 0–14.60% with a mean value of 4.0%. There was significant increase ($p < 0.001$) in the levels of HbF in samples of β -thalassemia trait when compared to normal samples by both CAE and HPLC techniques.

Comparison of levels of different Hb variants : A, A₂, F and S in each test group by HPLC and CAE are shown in Fig. 3. The separation and analyses of different haemoglobin fractions was best performed by HPLC with a high resolution and precision compared to CAE.

Fig. 3. Percentage mean of Hb type in each test group by HPLC and CAE.

Discussion

Thalassemia is the most common genetic disorder in

the world. As in other Mediterranean and Middle Eastern countries, β -thalassemia is an important health problem in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The β -thalassemias are more common along the coastal strip of the Red Sea and in the Eastern province around Jubail, Qateef, Damman and Hofuf of Saudi Arabia. Sickle cell disorders comprise 74% of all hemoglobinopathies in Saudi Arabia. We have undertaken the present study to analyze the presence of haemoglobin variants in Riyadh, as 2.08% carriers of sickle cell and 2.01% of thalassemia and 0.15% of the disease of both sickle and thalassemia were reported in Riyadh. The study was conducted to analyze the levels of Hb variants on 200 samples suspected of haemoglobinopathy collected at King Khalid University Hospital, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia using cellulose acetate electrophoresis (CAE) and HPLC method. The results obtained by both methods were compared in order to find out the best method for diagnosis.

The values obtained for haematological indices (Hb, Hct, MCV, MCH, MCHC and reticulocytes count) of normal healthy individuals in the present study are in accordance with reference range values of hematological parameters in Saudi healthy adults given by Al-Buhairan *et al.*¹³. Low values of MCV and MCH were observed in β -thalassemia patients.

Variation was observed in HbA values obtained by CAE with respect to normal subjects and patients with haemoglobinopathy. Decrease in HbA levels was observed for β -thalassemia patients with a mean value of 91.38 ± 4.39 , when compared with normal persons (97.5 ± 0.36), whereas, huge decrease in HbA levels was observed in patients with sickle cell trait (58.38 ± 11.65) as shown in Table 2. In patients with sickle cell disease HbA was not detected. Similar type of variation in HbA levels was observed by HPLC method with decrease of HbA levels in β -thalassemia patients (90.56 ± 5.0), much lower levels in patients with sickle cell trait (58.96 ± 12.69) and absence of HbA in patients with sickle cell disease.

The levels of HbA₂ vary between different methods and also by pre-analytical variables. In high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) the presence of haemoglobin variants such as HbS, HbE and Hb results in elevation of HbA₂ level. In this study, we found that the mean level of HbA₂ by CAE in a normal population was

2.39 ± 0.34 , however by HPLC the mean level of HbA₂ was 2.46 ± 0.24 . When HbA₂ levels were analyzed by CAE method, it was observed that there was increase in HbA₂ levels in patients with sickle cell trait (3.71 ± 0.95), sickle cell disease (3.72 ± 1.55) and in β -thalassemia patients (5.42 ± 1.08) when compared with normal subjects. Upon comparison of HbA₂ levels by HPLC method with CAE, variation was observed with respect to patients with haemoglobinopathies. Higher levels of HbA₂ were recorded for patients with sickle cell trait (4.15 ± 0.58), sickle cell disease (3.96 ± 1.43) and in β -thalassemia patients (5.44 ± 1.21). The increase in levels of HbA₂ was much higher in β -thalassemia patients which satisfy the diagnostic criteria for β -thalassemia. This conferred the levels of HbA₂ by CAE to be significantly lower range than that of HPLC. These findings were in agreement with a previous study by Higgins *et al.*, who reported the upper limit of the HbA₂ reference range to be 3.1% by CAE as compared to 3.6% by HPLC¹⁴.

Unlike HbA₂, an accurate determination of HbF level is less critical for the diagnosis of β -thalassemia carriers. HbF levels can either be normal or raised in β -thalassemia heterozygotes. The proportion of HbF in relation to other haemoglobin components could also help to determine thalassaemia phenotypes in compound heterozygous cases. In the present study HPLC method has shown better resolution in the levels of HbF than CAE method. Elevated levels of HbF were observed in patients with sickle cell trait (1.53 ± 2.06), sickle cell disease (16.54 ± 8.71) and in β -thalassemia patients (4.00 ± 4.92) when compared with normal subjects (0.40 ± 0.46). On the other hand CAE method could not resolve the HbF levels in all subjects, especially in normal healthy females. The levels of HbF obtained by CAE are 0.10 ± 0.32 for normal healthy males, sickle cell trait (0.79 ± 2.5), sickle cell disease (18.15 ± 9.41) and for thalassaemia patients (3.20 ± 4.61). These results obtained for HbF proves that HPLC is the better method than CAE for detecting haemoglobinopathies. In the present study we observed a higher variation in the levels of HbS in patients with sickle cell trait and sickle cell disease. Mean levels of HbS recorded by CAE are 37.10 ± 9.3 and 78.13 ± 8.25 for sickle cell trait and sickle cell disease whereas, with HPLC mean levels of HbS were 35.24 ± 10.78 and

79.5 ± 7.63 for sickle cell trait and sickle cell disease respectively.

In our study on samples of haemoglobin disorders of Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, we found that HbA₂ was the most prevalent haemoglobin variant that can act as molecular marker in diagnosis of β -thalassaemia and HbS for sickle cell disease. These molecular markers were best resolved by HPLC when compared to CAE. Based on the data obtained in this study, the type of β -thalassaemia identified in Riyadh population could be categorized as Type-I β -thalassaemia (high HbA₂ \pm HbF) which is geographically prevalent in Italian, Greek, African and Asian countries¹⁰.

The accurate determination of HbA₂ and F, and the detection of the haemoglobin variants, usually require time-consuming methods. The variant HPLC system provides a rapid, simple and reliable separation and determination of the relative percentage of different haemoglobin types, particularly haemoglobin A₂ and F, in whole blood. The method is accurate and reproducible. Other advantages are minimal sample preparation, a short analysis time, and the ability of the autosampler to analyze up to 100 samples sequentially and automatically. The reliability of HbA₂ measurement by HPLC for detection of β -thalassaemia without any false positive or negative result is of great advantage.

Conclusion

There was significant change in the values of haemoglobin variants-HbA₂, S and F in different types of haemoglobinopathies compared to normal subjects. HbS and HbF increases prominently in sickle cell disease and HbA₂ increases significantly in β -thalassaemia patients. It was found that CAE was inefficient quantifying HbF in normal healthy subjects and also HbA₂ values by CAE were not influenced by presence of HbS or any other variant. Finally we conclude that electrophoresis is slow, time consuming and poor in resolution compared to HPLC. The simplicity of sample preparation, high resolution, combined with complete automation makes HPLC, an ideal method for diagnosis of haemoglobin disorders in routine clinical laboratories with a high workload.

Conflict of interest : The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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